

CHEMISTRY

SOIL POLLUTION AROUND OIL REFINERIES WITH HEAVY METALS AND OIL PRODUCTS

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Abstract

This paper examines soil pollution near the Heydar Aliyev Baku Oil Refinery (BOR). The concentrations of petroleum hydrocarbons and heavy metals (Pb, Cd, Cr, Ni, Cu, etc.) in the soil were determined, and their impact on the physicochemical properties of the soil was assessed. The main pollutants in the area are oil and petroleum products, heavy metals, and other contaminants. Research shows that the soils around the BOR are seriously contaminated with heavy metals and petroleum products due to emissions, spills, and improper waste management, which degrades their properties, disrupts the environment, and poses a threat to human health. The results indicate that soil pollution in areas adjacent to the BOR poses a high environmental risk and requires ongoing monitoring.

Keywords: oil refinery, oil-contaminated soils, petroleum hydrocarbons, heavy metals, environmental risk.

The objective of the study was to determine the actual soil condition within the Heydar Aliyev Baku Oil Refinery.

Introduction

The oil refining industry occupies a significant place in Azerbaijan's industrial sector. However, the lengthy process of oil refining leads to environmental pollution, particularly of the soil. The environmental problems that have arisen around the Baku oil refinery are of immediate scientific and practical importance. Soil pollution around oil refineries has been extensively studied, and it has been established that petroleum products disrupt the soil structure, and heavy metals reduce the biological activity of the soil, posing a threat to ecosystems [1,2].

Heavy metals, the main group of elements polluting soils, have been a pressing environmental issue for decades, as high concentrations of them have a toxic effect on soil chemistry and plants. Soil is the primary environment where heavy metals enter from the atmosphere and water. Plants in such soil absorb the heavy metals, and some of them subsequently end up in food. The main sources of heavy metal soil pollution are the ferrous and non-ferrous metallurgy, energy production, mining, and other industries [3,4].

Soil pollution with industrial toxicants occurs in industrial cities, where the primary source of harmful substances is atmospheric air [1, 3]. Pollutants contained in industrial emissions combine with water vapor and gradually settle to the surface soil layer. Unlike atmospheric air, soil exhibits persistent, long-term contamination with chemicals specific to a given industrial sector [5, 6]. Toxicants can dissolve and migrate into living organisms through the food chain.

A second pathway for heavy metal salts and petroleum products to enter the soil is through pipeline accidents or the gradual spread of oil sludge from oil fields. The main heavy metals are lead, cadmium, mercury, and arsenic. They become hazardous when oil sludge enters groundwater. Volatile fractions of petroleum are highly toxic to soil organisms, but their effects are short-lived. The heavy fractions are immobile and can create persistent contamination in the soil, causing de-structuring. They disrupt moisture exchange, altering the hydrophysical properties and biological activity of the soil. Like pesticides, heavy metal salts accumulate in agricultural soils and subsequently migrate to plants. They enter the human body through the food chain via plant or animal products [7-11].

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted within a radius of 0–1.5 km from the Heydar Aliyev Baku Oil Refinery. Soil samples were collected from a depth of 0–20 cm and analyzed using infrared spectroscopy and atomic absorption analysis. Analysis methods include atomic absorption spectrometry. Soils can be cleaned of oil products using ultrasound, which disrupts the bonds between the soil and contaminants.

During 2024–2025, we collected 20 samples from the Heydar Aliyev Oil Refinery industrial zone and throughout the city. Sampling was conducted using the "envelope" method at a depth of 0–10 cm³ in eight directions from the petrochemical complex: north (N), south (S), east (E), west (W), northwest (NW), northeast (NE), southwest (SW), and southeast (SE) [12–14]. Concentrations of industrial toxicants were determined at the Baku State University Environmental Pollution Monitoring Laboratory. The obtained values for chemicals in the soil were compared with previous soil studies conducted at the Heydar Aliyev Oil Refinery.

Results and discussion

Due to the rapid development of the oil and chemical industries and the intensification of agricultural production, land pollution occurs as a result of accidental or uncontrolled leaks during the production, transportation, use, storage, and disposal of substances, which has a negative impact on the environment. This pollution is represented by oil, petroleum products (hy-

drocarbons), agricultural pesticides, and chemical industry products [15, 16]. Oil and petroleum products are among the main environmental pollutants, which, along with other pollutants, threaten not only the normal functioning of various ecosystems but also human existence. The most significant environmental damage is caused by accidents on main and in-field pipelines. Fig.1

Fig.1. Main causes of oil leaks.

Among pollutants, heavy metals occupy a special place in terms of the scale of pollution and impact on biological objects. Heavy metals contained in industrial waste are emitted into the atmosphere and deposited on the soil surface. The bulk of heavy metals is firmly fixed in the 0-10 cm layer of natural soils and 0-20 cm

of arable soils [17]. The soil type is mainly represented by ordinary chernozems and floodplain soils. The average pH was 7.4 units. The content of heavy metal salts in the soil on the territory of the Heydar Aliyev Oil Refinery is presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Metal	Concentration of heavy metals in soil (mg/kg)		Year
	Near Zone	Middle Zone	
Pb	120 65	25 32	2024-2025
Cd	3.5 1.8	0.5 1.0	2024-2025
Ni	95 50	30 40	2024-2025
Zn	67 34	36 42	2024-2025
Cu	45 22	34 47	2024-2025
Sn	36 17	31 42	2024-2025

The results of the analysis of samples with excess of MAC (maximum permissible concentrations) 1 MAC (approximate permissible concentration) are presented in Table 1. In 2025, the largest number of them were detected for cadmium in the zone with a radius of more than 1.5 km - 67% in the range from 1 MAC to 5 MAC and 10% more than 5 MAC, for copper - 19% more than 1 MAC, for nickel - 52% more than 1 MAC, for zinc - 57% more than 1 MAC. On the territory of the Heydar Aliyev Oil Refinery, excesses were detected

only for cadmium, copper and zinc more than 1 MAC in 36%, 45% and 100%, respectively [5-7].

When analyzing the content of petroleum products in the soil in 2025, which amounted to 53–4854 mg/kg, in 88% of the collected samples there was an excess of the background value by 1.1–97.1 times. On average, the level of petroleum products in the study area exceeded the background by 12.7 times and was equal to 634.84 mg/kg. The maximum content of petroleum

products was recorded in the buffer base of the oil refinery (4854 mg/kg, 97.08 F), which is lower than in 1999, when the average content of these impurities was observed at the level of 21 F, the maximum - 145 F. Extremely high pollution (more than 50 F) was observed in 4% of samples, high pollution (20–50 F) - in 10% of samples, soil pollution at the level of 2.0–18.9 F - in 56% of the collected samples. The detection of

elevated levels of petroleum products in the soil is related to the location of numerous oil refining and petrochemical plants. Figure 2 shows an area contaminated with oil waste around an oil refinery. In 2025, soil contamination studies were conducted according to the same program as in 2024. The soil type remained unchanged. The average pH was 8.3.

Fig. 2. The plant area contaminated with oil waste.

When studying the content of heavy metal salts, no samples exceeding the MAC (APC) were found for each representative. The average concentration of cadmium and zinc slightly exceeded the background level and amounted to 1.02 F and 1.06 F, respectively. This is explained by the fact that over 9 years, colossal work has been done to modernize oil refining and petrochemical enterprises. This is also evidenced by a steady decrease in total emissions of harmful substances into the

atmosphere of the Heydar Aliyev Oil Refinery from all stationary sources from 40.6 thousand tons in 2024 to 25.828 thousand tons in 2024. Unlike heavy metal salts, the content of petroleum products in the soil over the past 9 months increased from 634.84 mg / kg to 776.86 mg / kg. Table 2 shows the cases of exceeding background concentrations of petroleum products in the study area.

Table 2

Content of petroleum products in the soil of industrial zones of the Heydar Aliyev Baku Oil Refinery and in the city and their percentage exceeding background levels (in 2025, F = 50 mg/kg; in 2024, F = 38 mg/kg)

Year	Number of samples	Petroleum products				
		M ± m, mq/kg	Less 2 F	2-20 F	20-50 F	More 50 F
2024	10	634.84 ± 122.4	30	56	10	4
2025	10	776.86 ± 205.08	14	66	12	8

The maximum concentration of petroleum products was recorded in the industrial zone of the Heydar Aliyev Oil Refinery (8855.6 mg/kg, 233.04 F), which is almost twice as high as the maximum concentration recorded in 2024. Over the 9th month, the percentage of samples with extremely high contamination increased from 4% to 8%, and with high contamination – from 10% to 12%. There was also an increase in the number of samples with a level of 2–20 F from 56% to 66%. The change in the amount of petroleum hydrocarbons in the soil (graphical representation) depending on

the distance is shown in Figure 3. The results show that the amount of petroleum hydrocarbons in areas located near the plant exceeds the norm and decreases with increasing distance. The increase in the concentration of petroleum products in the soil on the territory of the Heydar Aliyev Oil Refinery over the 9th month is associated not only with the activities of oil refining and petrochemical enterprises, but also with the increase in the number of motor vehicle

Fig.3.Changes in elemental content during removal from the plant.

In 2025, the average cadmium, copper, nickel, and lead concentrations did not exceed the MAC (MPC) for loamy soils and ranged from 0.2 to 0.7 MPC (MPC). The maximum cadmium concentration was observed at 0.4 MPC in the industrial zone of the Heydar Aliyev Oil Refinery. The maximum copper content was observed at 4 ODK in a zone with a radius of 1.1–1.5 km to the east. The maximum nickel concentration was also recorded at 3 ODK. Elevated lead levels were detected at 1 ODK in a zone with a radius of 0.1–1.5 km to the southeast. The average cadmium and zinc concentrations exceeded the ODK and were at 3.05 ODK and 1.27 ODK, respectively. The maximum cadmium content was recorded at 10 ODK in a zone with a radius of 1.1–1.5 km to the northeast, and the maximum zinc content was at 4.1 ODK in a zone with a radius of 0–1.0 km to the south. The average concentrations of cadmium, copper, nickel, lead, and zinc exceeded background levels and were 8.7 F, 5.62 F, 1.63 F, 1.33 F, and 3.98 F, respectively. The average cadmium level did not exceed background levels and was recorded at 0.52 F.

From 2024 to 2025, concentrations of heavy metal salts in the soil decreased both within the Heydar Aliyev Oil Refinery industrial zone and within the city limits. Significant differences were observed in the soil concentrations of cadmium, copper, lead, nickel, and zinc in 2025 and 2024, respectively. Soil contamination with petroleum products remained virtually unchanged over the study period; however, a greater shift in the percentage of samples exceeding background levels was observed in 2020 compared to 2025. Analysis revealed that the total amount of petroleum hydrocarbons in areas adjacent to the refinery exceeds the permissible limit by 2–4 times. High concentrations of heavy metals, such as Pb and Cd, were detected.

Conclusion

A soil study was conducted in 2024–2025 at the Heydar Aliyev Oil Refinery in Baku. Concentrations of heavy metal salts and petroleum products were determined within the industrial zone and throughout the city. The study revealed that, compared to 2024, heavy metal salt concentrations in the soil decreased in 2025, both within the plant's industrial zone and within the city limits. Significant differences were found in the soil concentrations of cadmium, copper, lead, nickel, and zinc in 2025. Unlike heavy metal salts, petroleum product concentrations in the soil have shown an upward trend over the past nine months. The highest concentration of petroleum products was found within the plant's industrial zone.

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